

fungicidal activities at 1:100 000 concentration. In general, compounds having chlorine atom or methoxy group in 1-aryl nucleus exhibit higher fungitoxicity. Replacement of 4-OCH₃ group by 4-OC₂H₅ group has been found to decrease fungitoxicity. The ethylene disulphides were found to be better fungicides than the corresponding sulphides. The most active compounds of the series were 6, 7, 9 and 18 (Tables 1 and 2).

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Separation of Thorium from Trivalent Rare Earths in Monazite and its Gravimetric Determination using *o*-Carboxyphenylazo- β -naphthol

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THOUGH many methods of separating thorium from the cerite earths have been developed, each method has some complexity¹⁻⁴. Murthy and Rao⁵ and Rao and Rao⁶ have reported the use of *o*-chlorobenzoic acid and *o*- and *p*-aminobenzoic acid for the separation and estimation of thorium in monazite. In the present work, we report the use of *o*-carboxyphenylazo- β -naphthol (CPAN) in quantitatively precipitating thorium in the presence of ten-fold excess of lanthanum in a single precipitation at pH 5.3. Since in Indian monazite, the

ratio of ThO₂ to R₂O₃ is 1:8, the advantage offered by this reagent in the recovery of thorium from monazite becomes more apparent.

Experimental

Preparation of reagent: The azo dye CPAN was prepared by diazotising anthranilic acid and coupling it with β -naphthol which was purified earlier by sublimation. The dye was finally recrystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 265-70°. The dye was insoluble in water and slightly soluble in most of the common organic solvents and was freely soluble in dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO) (Found: C, 69.5; H, 4.2; N, 9.3. C₁₇H₁₂N₂O₃ calcd. for: C, 69.86; H, 4.11; N, 9.59%).

A solution of thorium nitrate, using Th(NO₃)₄.4H₂O was prepared and standardised with 10% oxalic acid solution. Solutions of nitrates of lanthanum, uranium and zirconium oxychloride were also prepared. All the chemicals employed were of analytical grade.

Procedure: To the stock solution (20 ml) containing thorium (50 mg), acetate-acetic acid buffer was added, followed by twice the volume of DMSO. pH of the solution was adjusted with a pH meter. It was established that a minimum of 2:1 ratio of DMSO to water must be maintained in the reaction mixture to keep the dye in solution. The reagent (100 mg) was added to the above solution with continuous stirring. The precipitate was digested over boiling water-bath for 1 h and filtered through Whatman no. 41 filter paper. The precipitate was washed several times with water, dried, ignited to ThO₂ and weighed.

Results and Discussion

Study at various pH: The precipitation of thorium under different conditions of pH was investigated. It was noticed that the precipitation was not complete when the pH was 5.0 or lower. The complete precipitation occurs at pH range 5.3-7.0.

Interference of other ions: The interference of 8-fold excess of La⁺⁺⁺ at various pH was investigated. It was noticed that the precipitation of thorium was incomplete at pH 5, and at pH 5.5 rare earths started to precipitate. The optimal pH for the precipitation of thorium without the interference of rare earths was found to be 5.3. The study of interference of Zr⁺⁺⁺, UO₂⁺⁺⁺, Ce⁺⁺⁺ and La⁺⁺⁺ was carried out at pH 5.3. Amount of La⁺⁺⁺ varied from 2 to 10 times the amount of Th. It was found that none of these ions causes any interference at this particular pH.

Composition of thorium complex: Analysis of the metal content of the complex displayed the metal-ligand ratio to be 1:2. C, H, N analysis was also done (Found: Th, 28.07; C, 51.25; H, 2.94, N, 6.82. Th[C₁₇H₁₀N₂O₃]₂

calculated for: Th, 28.57; C, 50.24; H, 2.46; N, 6.89%). The ir spectrum of the thorium chelate indicated the absence of characteristic absorptions for OH and COOH groups. However, the strong absorption of the ligand at 1700 cm^{-1} due to γ ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) is shifted to lower frequencies in the chelate and appears at 1600 cm^{-1} . A strong band at 1450 cm^{-1} ($\text{N}=\text{N}$) is shifted to 1400 cm^{-1} in the complex. These shifts towards lower frequencies show that $\text{N}=\text{N}$ and $\text{C}=\text{O}$ are involved in bond formation. The TGA data also support 1 : 2 complex.

Estimation of thorium in monazite: Powdered monazite sand was converted into a mixture of thorium and rare earth sulphates by heating with concentrated H_2SO_4 . Accurately weighed quantities of Travancore monazite were digested with 3-4 times its weight of concentrated H_2SO_4 for 4 h at $200\text{-}250^\circ$. The mass was extracted with ice-cold water. Thorium and rare earth metals were precipitated by oxalic acid. Reprecipitation was carried out. The precipitate was dissolved in concentrated HNO_3 and the excess acid evaporated to dryness. The residue was dissolved in water and acetate-acetic acid buffer was added to adjust the pH at 5.3 and Th was estimated with CPAN according to the procedure detailed above. Similar experiments was conducted using fresh samples of monazite. Th is precipitated as iodate by standard procedure⁷. Thorium iodate is converted into oxalate by using oxalic acid. Finally, thorium oxalate is ignited to ThO_2 , dried and weighed.

ThO_2 contents in monazite obtained through these two methods are comparable: iodate method, 8.99%; and CPAN method, 9.00%.

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Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Trace Amounts of Molybdenum with Benzyltriethylammonium Chloride

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A number of quaternary ammonium salts have been reported to find application in the determination of a large number of metal ions in small

concentration in solution. Yoshimura and Ueno¹ used benzyltrimethylphenylammonium chloride in the spectrophotometric determination of cobalt(II), iron(III), copper(II) and molybdenum(V) in SCN^- solutions. The same reagent was employed for the gravimetric determination of platinum² and extractive spectrophotometric determination of bismuth³ and palladium⁴. Benzyltriethylammonium chloride in SCN^- solution reacts with many metallic ions with the formation of coloured precipitate. The present work describes a highly sensitive and selective method for the extractive spectrophotometric determination of molybdenum(V) in trace concentrations using benzyltriethylammonium chloride as reagent and 1,2-dichloroethane as the extracting solvent.

Experimental

A Hilger Uvispek photoelectric spectrophotometer with matched quartz cells of 1 cm optical path was used.

The stock solution of molybdenum was prepared from molybdenum trioxide (A.R.) and was standardised by known method⁵. Test solutions of lower concentration were prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock. The reagent, benzyltriethylammonium chloride, was prepared⁶ by refluxing for 1 h a mixture of ethyl acetate, dimethylformamide, triethylamine and benzylchloride. A 0.01 M solution of benzyltriethylammonium chloride, a 3 M solution of potassium thiocyanate and a saturated solution (18 M) of thiourea were prepared in distilled water. All chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Procedure: An aliquot of the solution containing 4-80 μg of molybdenum was made acidic with 18 M H_2SO_4 (2 ml). To this the thiourea solution (8 ml), the potassium thiocyanate solution (4 ml) and then the benzyltriethylammonium chloride solution (5 ml) were added. The total volume was made up to 25 ml with distilled water. The resulting solution after having mixed with 1,2-dichloroethane (20 ml) was shaken for 3 min, and the organic layer separated. Absorbance of the extract was measured at 465 nm against the pure solvent. Amount of molybdenum in unknown solutions was calculated from the standard calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Benzyltriethylammonium chloride (QCl) reacts with the SCN^- -complex of molybdenum(V) yielding the ion-pair $\text{Q}^+ [\text{Mo}(\text{SCN})_6]^-$ in the form of an orange-yellow precipitate. The ion-pair is completely extractable into 1,2-dichloroethane and the extract absorbs maximum at 465 nm. Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration range 0.2-4.0 ppm of molybdenum. The reagent blank shows no absorption at this wave length. Molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity are $1.79 \times 10^4\text{ l mol}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0053\text{ }\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$, respectively.